

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Prototype of a UAV-spray system for aerial spraying applications

SPOKE 6 – Primary Agroindustry

DELIVERABLE D5.2

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organise their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated with the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organised by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A) **Prototype of a UAV-spray system for aerial spraying applications**

Prototype description, technical specifications, test measurements and photos.

Description of the UAV

Drone with high carrying capacity and long range. It is a custom drone with mechanical/electrical interface that can be customised to accommodate different payloads and compatible with interfaces for Matrix 600 and for Matrix 300.

The Kit delivered on 19/09/2023 contains the UAV (Ready for Fly) based on high-performance hexacopter frame, Cube Orange type Pixhawk 2 flight controller featuring triple redundancy and integrated ADS-B receiver, RTK GPS with base station (EMLID kit "multi-band Emlid Reach M2 UAV Mapping") configured and integrated into the system.

A high-performance data link enables reception of video and ground data on the Ground Station.

3 sets of Batteries (25000mAh CAD capacity) and 2 chargers are included.

The Custom Drone frame, white in colour, features Removable Arms for ease of transport and has been provided with a special sturdy transport case for carrying the drone. 3 spare propellers are included.

For safety issues, it is provided with a flight terminator with integrated parachute that can be operated automatically or by trigger from flight terminator.

Technical specifications

- MTOW < 25KG
- Payload capacity ≥ 10 KG
- Autonomy with maximum load ≥ 10 min.

Testing sessions

The flight test sessions of the prototype were as follows:

- 21/06/2023 UAV testing on Aermatica HQ, issues with RTK antenna link
- 19/09/2023 Delivering and testing of the drone on Aermatica HQ.
- 14/11/2023 Field test on DiSAFA experimental fields in Carmagnola (TO), telemetry data

visualisation issues detected. Parachute link malfunction.

- 12/12/2023 Drone delivered to Aermatica in order to fix the issues raised during the field test.

Photo of the prototype

Figures 1,2,3 and 4 show the UAV prototype and its main components.

Figure 1 - Smart controller

Figure 2 - Battery charging station and batteries.

Figure 3 - UAV prototype at Aermatica HQ

Figure 4 - UAV prototype during flying test